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Research Article

Assessment Of Incidence & Pattern of Drug Induced Gastrointestinal Disorder in a Tertiary Care Teaching Hospital

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ABSTRACT

Drug-induced gastrointestinal (GI) disorders represent a significant clinical issue, contributing to increased patient morbidity and healthcare costs, particularly with the widespread use of medications such as NSAIDs and antibiotics in tertiary care hospitals. This prospective observational study was conducted over three months in a tertiary care teaching hospital with 150 patients receiving medications known to cause GI side effects. The study aimed to assess the incidence, patterns, commonly implicated drugs, severity, and preventability of drug-induced GI disorders. Among the participants (55% female, 45% male; mean age 45 years, most common age group 18-30 years), 20 cases (13%) of GI disorders were identified, predominantly presenting as nausea and vomiting (75%), followed by peptic ulcers (10%) and diarrhea (10%). Antibiotics, especially penicillin and fluoroquinolones, were the most frequently associated drugs. Most adverse drug reactions (ADRs) were classified as probable (85%), with 45% being predictable, and 35% deemed definitely preventable. The incidence rate was calculated as 0.5333 cases per patient-year. These findings underscore the need for enhanced Pharmacovigilance and optimization of drug administration protocols to reduce preventable ADRs and improve patient safety in hospital settings.

INTRODUCTION

Adverse Drug Reactions (ADRs) are defined as any harmful, unintended, and undesirable effects of a drug that occur at normal doses used for prevention, diagnosis, or treatment.

Gastrointestinal (GI) ADRs are among the most common and can significantly affect patient health and treatment outcomes. Examples include antibiotic-induced constipation and diarrhea, NSAID-induced peptic ulcers, GI bleeding, and drug-induced hepatotoxicity.^{1,2,3} GI diseases affect the digestive tract, including the mouth,

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esophagus, stomach, intestines, liver, gallbladder, and pancreas. Drug-induced GI disorders may resemble conditions like irritable bowel syndrome (IBS) or inflammatory bowel disease (IBD), making diagnosis challenging. These disorders may result from altered GI physiology (e.g., constipation from anticholinergics), direct tissue damage (e.g., ulcers from NSAIDs), disruption of gut microbiota (e.g., *C. difficile* infection from antibiotics), or unknown mechanisms such as those seen with metformin. 4,5 Antibiotic-Associated Diarrhea (AAD) is a common side effect of antibiotic use, occurring during or up to two months after treatment. It ranges from mild diarrhea to severe GI symptoms like abdominal pain, constipation, and flatulence. AAD results from the imbalance of gut bacteria, and nearly all antibiotics can potentially cause it.6 Non-Steroidal Anti-Inflammatory Drugs (NSAIDs) are widely used for pain and inflammation but are major contributors to GI toxicity. Most non-*H. pylori* peptic ulcers are caused by NSAIDs due to the inhibition of protective prostaglandin synthesis. Symptoms include abdominal pain, nausea, vomiting, bloating, and loss of appetite. Severe complications can lead to anaemia, bleeding, or perforation. To reduce risks, NSAIDs should be used cautiously, especially in elderly patients. When necessary, co-administration with proton pump inhibitors (PPIs) or misoprostol is recommended to protect the GI lining. 7,8,9,10 Pharmaceutical preparations are a major cause of liver injury, with hepatotoxicity being the leading cause of acute liver failure. The liver, as the primary organ for drug metabolism and elimination, is vulnerable to damage from various drugs such as anti-tubercular agents, anesthetics, paracetamol, anti-cancer drugs, steroids, vaccines, and antivirals—especially with long-term use. Hepatotoxic reactions may be predictable (dose-related and occurring shortly after exposure) or unpredictable (not dose-related and with delayed

onset). It is essential to assess patients thoroughly before prescribing hepatotoxic drugs, monitor liver enzymes regularly, use the lowest effective doses, and educate patients to report symptoms early for timely intervention. 11,12 The review of literature presents various studies addressing upper gastrointestinal complications related to NSAID use, highlighting prevalence, risk factors, and associated patient outcomes. It summarizes research that investigates the incidence of bleeding, ulceration, and drug-related GI events in different populations, often comparing NSAID use to control groups or other therapies. Other studies focus on comorbid conditions, diagnostic patterns, prognostic markers, and management strategies, revealing consistently higher GI risk in patients exposed to NSAIDs and related medications, especially in those with comorbid illnesses or predisposing factors. Taken together, these findings emphasize the clinical importance of monitoring and mitigating gastrointestinal risks in patients receiving NSAID therapy across diverse patient populations.

Pharmacists play a vital role in managing and preventing drug-induced gastrointestinal (GI) disorders. They can reduce antibiotic-associated GI issues and NSAID-induced ulcers through patient counseling, medication reviews, recommending probiotics or gastroprotective agents, and providing dietary advice. By collaborating with healthcare providers, they help ensure safer medication choices and promote adherence to monitoring protocols. So this study was conducted to analyze the frequency, patterns, and real-world impact of GI adverse drug reactions. The findings will support better prescribing practices, improve pharmacovigilance, and enhance patient safety in order to enhance and develop the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of Govt. of India.

MATERIALS ANE METHODS: 8

A prospective observational study was conducted at Department of Gastroenterology, Navodaya Medical College Hospital and Research Center, which is a tertiary care teaching hospital over a duration of three months and included a sample size of 150 patients. Patients eligible for inclusion were those admitted to the hospital during the study period and receiving antibiotic treatment, NSAIDs, or other medications known to cause gastrointestinal (GI) side effects. Additionally, only patients with a confirmed diagnosis of drug-induced gastrointestinal disease, supported by medical records, were considered. Exclusion criteria comprised patients not admitted to the hospital, those with pre-existing gastrointestinal diseases that could confound the assessment of drug-induced effects, individuals unable to provide accurate information about their symptoms or medication history, and patients with incomplete medical records that would hinder establishing a clear link between drug exposure and GI disease. Furthermore, patients with severe co-morbidities that could independently affect gastrointestinal health (such as advanced cancer, or severe liver or kidney disease), as well as pregnant or breastfeeding women, were excluded from the study. The study was approved Institutional Ethical Committee of study hospital by using ethical clearance certificate.

Sample Size Calculation⁹:

$P= 0.096, Z= 3.8416$ at 95% CI, $d= 0.000025$

$n=z^2 \times p(1-p)/d^2$ So, $n= 133.2= 150$

The project team visited the study ward on a routine basis, recorded the cases, monitored for possible adverse drug reactions (ADRs), and interacted with patients to determine if they experienced any gastrointestinal (GI) side effects

after the administration of the suspected drugs. GI ADRs were obtained, were assessed for causality by using Naranjo Scale and confirmed it through AMC of study hospital. The collected information was compiled in MS Excel and analyzed using descriptive statistics to determine the incidence & pattern of drug induced gastrointestinal disorder.

Statistical Analysis:

The data collected was consolidated in an MS Excel spread sheet (2007 version). The data was meticulously checked for completeness and accuracy. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies and percentages were used to analyze the data.

RESULTS

"Assessment of Incidence and Pattern of Drug-Induced Gastrointestinal Disorders in a Tertiary Care Teaching Hospital" was conducted on 150 patients at Navodaya Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Raichur.

DEMOGRAPHIC DETAILS OF PATIENTS

The study population was predominantly aged 18–60 years (80%), with the highest proportions in the 18–30 (23%) and 31–40 (22%) age groups; the mean age was 45 with the standard deviation of 14.37. Unlike many ADR studies focusing on older adults, this younger demographic may still face risks due to lifestyle factors and drug exposure. Females comprised 55% of participants, aligning with other studies where women show higher ADR incidence, possibly due to hormonal, metabolic differences, and higher medication use for GI conditions like GERD and Irritable Bowel Syndrome. Data were shown in Table No 1 & Fig No 1. The male to female ratio was 9:11.

Fig.1: Gender Distribution (n=150)

Table 1: Age Distribution of Study Participants (n=150)

Age Group (Years)	Number of Participants	Percentage (%)
18-30	34	23
31-40	33	22
41-50	24	16
51-60	28	19
61-70	22	15
71-80	09	5
Mean Age	=	45 years

As shown in Table No. 2 we found that 69% of patients were non-users of tobacco or alcohol, while 11% were smokers, and 7% consumed

alcohol. It was important to noted that smoking and alcohol use were known to exacerbate the risk of drug-induced gastrointestinal disorders, especially when combined with medications like NSAIDs and corticosteroids, which already predispose individuals to ulcers and GI bleeding.

Table 2: Social History of Study Participants (n=150)

Habit	No. of Patients	Percentage (%)
Smoker	16	11
Alcoholic	10	7
Tobacco User	20	13
Non-User	104	69

We observed that several laboratory investigations were performed on patients with hemoglobin levels and white blood cell counts being the most common tests performed (Table 3). These investigations reflect the need to monitor drug effects on systemic health, especially when GI disorders can result in complications like anemia. Other diagnostic procedures included ultrasound scans (17%), smear tests (20%), and other imaging techniques , which help in diagnosing the severity and possible secondary effects of GI ADRs.Data was Shown in Fig. 2

Table 3: Laboratory Investigations Performed on Study Participants(n=400)

Test	No of Patients	Percentage (%)
Hemoglobin (Hb%)	100	25
White Blood Cells (WBC)	80	20
Packed Cell Volume (PCV)	70	17
Mean Corpuscular Volume (MCV)	60	15
Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin Concentration (MCHC)	50	13
Others*	40	10

* Include MCH, HIV, Platelet, RDW-CV, TSH, RBC.

Fig 2: Other Investigations Performed on Study Participants (n=150)

The reasons for hospital admissions showed a diverse range of diagnoses, with ovarian cystic disorders (17%) and hypothyroidism (17%) being prominent (**Fig. 3**). Although these conditions are not directly linked to GI disorders, the medications

used, such as NSAIDs or thyroid medications, can contribute to ADRs. The need for early monitoring and preventive care in high-risk patients was evident.

Fig 3: Reason for Admission of Study Participants (n=150)

Majority of ADRs were identified during ward rounds (75%) (**Table 4**). This reflects the importance of regular patient monitoring in detecting and addressing ADRs promptly.

that the risk of an ADR (Drug induced G.I Disorders) in a study population is decreased.

Table 4: ADR Identification Methods (n=20)

Method of Identification	No. of ADRs	Percentage (%)
Ward Rounds	15	75
Special Visit	05	25

Incidence of drug induced G.I disorders was calculated using the appropriate formula and found as 0.5333 Cases/Patient-Years. The Incidence value or Incidence rate is a measure of how often an event occurs over a specific period of time. An Incidence rate that is less than one percent means

Incidence of Drug Induced G.I Disorder

$$\text{Incidence Rate} = \frac{\text{New cases}}{\text{Population} \times \text{Time frame}}$$

Convert patient-months to patient-years

$$\text{Incidence Rate} = \frac{20 \text{ New cases} \times 1 \text{ months} \times 12 \text{ months}}{150 \text{ patients} \times 3}$$

$$\text{Incidence Rate} = \frac{20 \text{ New cases}}{150 \text{ patients}} \times 4 / \text{Year}$$

$$\text{Incidence Rate} = \frac{80 \text{ New cases}}{150 \text{ patient-year}}$$

$$\text{Incidence Rate} = 0.5333 \text{ Cases / Patients-Year}$$

Among the 20 documented gastrointestinal (G.I.) adverse drug reactions (ADRs), nausea and vomiting were most common, affecting 75% of patients, particularly those on antibiotics, chemotherapy, and NSAIDs. Peptic ulcer disease (PUD) occurred in 10% of participants, mainly linked to NSAID use, which impairs gastric mucosal protection. Diarrhea, also reported in 10% of cases, was largely associated with antibiotics—especially penicillin (35%), fluoroquinolones (25%), and nitroimidazoles (15%). These findings highlight the need for careful monitoring of high-risk drugs to ensure better patient safety and adherence which was depicted at **Table No. 5**

Table 5: Types of Drug-Induced GI Disorders Observed (n=20)

Type of GI Disorder	No. of Cases	Percentage (%)
Nausea and Vomiting	15	75
Peptic Ulcers	02	10
Hepatitis	01	5
Diarrhea	02	10

As Shown in **Fig. 4** the most commonly implicated drug classes for ADRs included penicillin antibiotics (25%) and fluoroquinolones (25%), followed by nitroimidazoles (15%) and NSAIDs (10%). These medications are well-documented for their GI side effects, including nausea, ulcers, and diarrhea. Co-prescription of gastroprotective agents, such as proton pump inhibitors, could have mitigated the risks.

Fig 4: Drugs Most Commonly Associated with GI Disorders (n=20)

Causality and Severity of GI Disorders: Most gastrointestinal ADRs were mild (50%) or moderate (35%), with only 15% classified as severe, primarily involving peptic ulcers and antibiotic-associated diarrhea. While the majority were manageable, the presence of severe cases highlights the importance of early detection and timely intervention. Causality assessment using Naranjo’s scale showed that 85% of the reactions were "probable," indicating a strong link between drug use and the GI disorders observed. Details were shown in Table 6 & Table 7

Table 6: Severity of Drug-Induced GI Disorders (n=20)

Severity Level	Number of Cases	Percentage (%)
Mild	10	50
Moderate	07	35
Severe	03	15

Table 7: Naranjo’s Causality Assessment of Drug-Induced GI Disorders (n=20)

Causality Category	No. of Cases	Percentage (%)
Certain	00	0
Probable	17	85
Possible	03	15

Preventability and Predictability: About 45% of ADRs were predictable based on known drug profiles, particularly for NSAIDs and antibiotics. Preventability analysis revealed that 35% of cases were definitely preventable and 65% probably preventable. This suggests a significant portion of GI ADRs could have been avoided through better prescribing practices, such as co-prescribing PPIs with NSAIDs or probiotics with antibiotics which was shown in **Fig. 5**

Fig. 5: Preventability of Drug Induced GI Disorder(n=20)

Predisposing Factors: The most common predisposing factor was multiple drug therapy (40%), followed by older age (25%) and gender (20%). These findings stress the need for individualized treatment approaches and careful monitoring of high-risk patients to reduce the incidence of drug-induced GI disorders which was shown in **Fig.6**

Fig. 6: Predisposing Factor of Drug Induced GI Disorder(n=20)

DISCUSSION

The present study comprehensively reveals the real-world burden of drug-induced gastrointestinal (GI) disorders in a tertiary care hospital, with an incidence of 13.3% among 150 patients and a calculated incidence rate of 0.5333 cases per patient-year. This rate, though appearing modest numerically, represents a significant clinical concern due to the avoidable nature of most cases. A notable dominance of nausea and vomiting (75%) as the primary symptom reflects the typical gastrointestinal impact of commonly used medications such as antibiotics and NSAIDs, which were the leading culprits. Penicillins and fluoroquinolones each accounted for 25% of the ADRs, followed by nitroimidazoles (15%) and NSAIDs (10%). These findings align with established pharmacological profiles, emphasizing how frequently prescribed drug classes can compromise GI safety if not co-managed with protective strategies. Importantly, the study showed that 35% of the reactions were definitely preventable, and 45% were predictable—indicating a serious gap in preventive pharmacotherapy. The absence of routine use of proton pump inhibitors with NSAIDs or probiotics with antibiotics appears to be a missed opportunity for risk mitigation. This preventability rate implies that a considerable fraction of these adverse effects could have been anticipated and avoided with standard precautionary measures. The demographic profile, with 55% female participants and a mean age of 45 years, adds depth to the clinical interpretation, as females and the younger adult population are not typically viewed as high-risk for GI ADRs. Yet, this study brings attention to the fact that drug-induced GI disorders are not limited to the elderly, especially in the context of polypharmacy, which was a predisposing factor in 40% of cases. Furthermore, most ADRs were classified as mild to moderate (85%), yet 15% were severe, including peptic ulcers and hepatitis, especially since 75% of ADRs were detected

during regular ward rounds—highlighting the crucial role of bedside pharmacovigilance. The causality analysis using Naranjo's scale placed 85% of the ADRs under the "probable" category, reinforcing a strong drug-event linkage. This strengthens the argument that many GI complications in hospitalized patients are iatrogenic and modifiable through better prescribing practices. In summary, the study makes it evident that drug-induced GI disorders remain a prevalent and preventable problem in hospital settings. The data calls for integrated intervention, including:

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